

Isocarotane Esters from *Ferula jaeschkeana*

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Two new isocarotane esters have been isolated from the methanolic extract of *Ferula jaeschkeana* rhizomes. These have been characterised as 5 α -4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol and 5 α -3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol on the basis of spectral and chemical analysis.

The genus *Ferula* distributed from Mediterranean region to Central Asia, is chemically characterised by its production of coumarin and sesquiterpenes¹. This genus is reported to possess emenagogue, abortifacient and uterine stimulant activities². *Ferula jaeschkeana* is distributed abundantly in the Himalayan range of India at an elevation of 2000–4000 m. Sesquiterpene esters and coumarins isolated from *F. jaeschkeana*, viz. ferujol, 5 α -3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzoate of jaeschkeanadiol, 5 α -4'-hydroxybenzoate of jaeschkeanadiol and 5 α -(4'-hydroxybenzoyl)-9 β -angeloxyjaeschkeanadiol showed potent antifertility and hormonal properties. In continuation of our studies on the sesquiterpene constituents of rhizomes of *F. jaeschkeana*, we describe here the isolation and structure elucidation of two new isocarotane esters, viz. 5 α -4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol and 5 α -3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol from the methanolic extract of the plant rhizomes.

Results and Discussion

5 α -4'-Hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol (1): It was obtained as colourless needles, C₂₂H₂₈O₄ (M⁺ 356). Its ir spectrum showed the presence of hydroxyl (3250 cm⁻¹), 1690 (ester carbonyl) and 1610 cm⁻¹ (aromatic) functions. The uv absorption at 255 nm and mass fragment at *m/z* 218 [M⁺-H₂O-C₆H₄(OH)COOH] indicate it to be *p*-hydroxybenzoate. The presence of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid group (*para*-substituted benzene) was further supported by ¹H nmr signals at δ 7.95 (2H, dd, *J* 8, 2 Hz) and 6.89 (2H, dd, *J* 8, 2

Hz). The ¹³C nmr spectrum of **1** showed 22 signals assigned for ester carbonyl, oxyphenyl, aromatic, olefinic, oxymethine and secondary and quaternary methyl carbons, confirming its structure to be that of *p*-hydroxybenzoate of the C₁₅ unsaturated alcohol ferujaesenol. Its saponification with alcoholic KOH gave *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid and ferujaesenol **3**, C₁₅H₂₄O₂, the structure and stereochemistry of which have already been established by us earlier³. The shift of CHOR signal from δ 5.22 in case of R = *p*-hydroxybenzoyl to 3.73 in case of R = H³ supported the existence of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid in ester link with secondary hydroxyl group of ferujaesenol. Hence, **1** is taken as 5 α -4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol.

5 α -3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol (2): It, C₂₃H₃₀O₅ (M⁺ 386), was obtained as colourless needles. λ_{\max} at 265 and 290 nm are due to the presence of 3–4 disubstituted aromatic ring. Bathochromic shifts in uv at 295 and 312 nm by the addition of alkali similar to that of yashferin, suggest the presence of *p*-hydroxybenzoyl system. Its ir spectrum showed intensive bands at 3300 (OH), 1695 (ester carbonyl) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring). Mass fragments at *m/z* 343 [M-C₃H₇]⁺, 218 [M-C₈H₈O₄]⁺, 175 [M-C₃H₇-C₈H₈O₄]⁺ and 168 [C₈H₈O₄]⁺ are characteristic of the esters of sesquiterpene alcohols with aromatic acids.

The doublets at δ 6.95 (*J* 8 Hz), 7.55 (*J* 2 Hz) and double doublet at δ 7.90 (*J* 8, 2 Hz) relate to the proton of vanillic acid supported by a singlet at δ 3.96 (3H) in its ¹H nmr for aromatic methoxyl group. On saponification with alcoholic KOH it gave vanillic acid and an alcohol, ferujaesenol **3**. Linkage of vanillic acid in ester with secondary hydroxyl group of ferujaesenol was revealed by the shift of CHOR proton signal from δ 5.26 as in **1** in the case of R = vanillyl **2** to δ 3.91 in the case of R = H (ferujaesenol **3**). Hence, compound **2** is characterised 5 α -3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol which is in quite agreement with its ¹³C nmr data.

Experimental

F. jaeschkeana rhizomes, collected from Gulmarg (Kashmir) in November 1991, were air-dried (1 kg), powdered and extracted in a soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), CHCl₃ and MeOH successively and concentrated under vacuum to yield three different fractions. Methanolic extract (40 g) was chromatographed on

SiO₂ (1 kg) column eluting with chloroform, CHCl₃/MeOH mixtures (95 : 5, 90 : 10, 50 : 50) and finally with methanol. The concentrated CHCl₃/MeOH (95 : 5) eluate (10 g) on rechromatography on SiO₂ column using CHCl₃/MeOH (1 to 10%) followed by preparative layer chromatography of CHCl₃-MeOH (92 : 8) eluate on SiO₂ plates (developed in CHCl₃-MeOH, 95 : 5) yielded two compounds of R_f 0.36 and 0.41 designated as 5 α -4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol (1) and 5 α -3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol (2) respectively. These gave violet colour on SiO₂ tlc plates when sprayed with vanillin in H₂SO₄ followed by heating for 10 min at 100°.

5 α -4'-Hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol (1, 40 mg), m.p. 121°, [α]_D²¹ + 70° (c = 2.5, CHCl₃); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 255, (MeOH + KOH) 290 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3250, 2940, 1690, 1658, 1610, 1590, 1510, 1435, 1370, 1315, 1240, 1165, 1090, 840 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (400 MHz, CDCl₃) 0.88 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, H-12), 0.92 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, H-13), 1.56 (3H, s, H-14), 1.81 (3H, s, H-15), 1.87 (1H, qq, J 7 Hz, H-11) 2.21 (1H, dd, J 15, 2 Hz, H_a-4), 2.32 (1H, br d, J 17 Hz, H_a-8), 2.42 (1H, br d, J 17 Hz, H_b-8), 2.48 (1H, m, H_a-1), 2.52 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-6), 2.65 (1H, dd, J 15, 7.5 Hz, H_b-1), 2.68 (1H, dd, J 15, 10 Hz, H_b-4), 5.22 (1H, td, J 10, 3 Hz, H-5), 5.58 (1H, m, H-2), 6.89 (2H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.95 (2H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-3' and 5'); ¹³C nmr δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 166.64 (s, C-7'), 161.30 (s, C-4') 135.30 (s, C-3)*, 132.13 (s, C-9)*, 131.60 (d, C-2' and C-6'), 126.94 (s, C-10), 123.20 (d, C-2)+, 122.31 (d, C-1')+ , 81.34 (s, C-7), 72.10 (d, C-5), 61.35 (d, C-6), 47.12 (t, C-1), 41.61 (t, C-8), 38.31 (d, C-11), 31.60 (t, C-4), 26.14 (q, C-15), 24.92 (q, C-14), 16.91 (q, C-12), 13.55 (q, C-13) [* , + signals are interchangeable]; *m/z* (rel. int.) 356 (C₂₂H₂₈O₄) [M]⁺ (8), 339 (18), 338 (80), 313 (7), 218 (10), 200 (55), 193 (10), 175 (45), 157 (30), 147 (55), 148 (20), 138 (21), 133 (25), 122 (70), 121 (100), 119 (40), 43 (80), 41 (22).

Hydrolysis of compound 1 : Compound 1 (20 mg) was refluxed with 4% methanolic KOH (2 ml) for 2 h and then processed for the isolation of neutral and acidic parts as usual. The acidic fraction of R_f 0.85 (CHCl₃-MeOH-CH₃COOH, 90 : 16 : 8) showed a single spot, identical to that of an authentic sample of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, m.p. 210–12°. The neutral fraction gave the alcohol ferujaesenol 3, m.p. 127–28°, C₁₅H₂₄O₂ (identical by co-comparison of

authentic ferujaesenol).

5 α -3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzoylferujaesenol (2), m.p. 155°, [α]_D²¹ + 95° (c = 2.0, CHCl₃); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 265, 290, (MeOH + KOH) 295, 312 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3300, 2960, 1695, 1658, 1600, 1590, 1525, 1440, 1365, 1310, 1240, 1200, 1155, 1100, 925 and 850 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (400 MHz, CDCl₃) 0.84 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, H-12), 0.89 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, H-13), 1.58 (3H, s, H-14), 1.77 (3H, s, H-15), 1.82 (1H, qq, J 7 Hz, H-11), 2.19 (1H, dd, J 15, 2 Hz, H_a-4), 2.34 (1H, br d, J 17 Hz, H_a-8), 2.46 (1H, br d, J 17 Hz, H_b-8), 2.51 (1H, m, H_a-1), 2.54 (1H, br d, J 10 Hz, H-6), 2.60 (1H, dd, J 15, 10 Hz, H_b-4), 2.72 (1H, dd, J 15, 7.5 Hz, H_b-1) 3.96 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.26 (1H, td, J 10, 3 Hz, H-5), 5.56 (1H, m, H-2), 6.95 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-5'), 7.55 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-2'), 7.90 (1H, dd, J 8, 2 Hz, H-6'); ¹³C nmr δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 166.32 (s, C-7'), 150.40 (s, C-3'), 146.20 (s, C-4'), 135.10 (s, C-3)*, 132.34 (s, C-9)*, 126.38 (s, C-10), 125.40 (d, C-6')+ , 123.40 (d, C-2)+, 122.61 (s, C-1'), 115.1 (d, C-5'), 113.12 (d, C-2'), 81.21 (s, C-7), 72.20 (d, C-5), 61.44 (d, C-6), 56.20 (q, OCH₃), 47.23 (t, C-1), 41.30 (t, C-8), 38.71 (d, C-11), 31.52 (t, C-4), 26.08 (q, C-15), 24.84 (q, C-14), 16.93 (q, C-12), 13.74 (q, C-13) [* , + signals are interchangeable]; *m/z* (rel. int.) 386 (C₂₃H₃₀O₅) M⁺ (10), 369 (15), 368 (80), 343 (9), 218 (15), 200 (80), 175 (33), 168 (15), 157 (21), 152 (65), 151 (100), 147 (52), 122 (35), 55 (21), 43 (80), 41 (23).

Hydrolysis of compound 2 : Compound 2 (20 mg) was hydrolysed with methanolic KOH to give the alcohol ferujaesenol 3 and vanillic acid.

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